

**ASSESSMENT OF THE OCCUPATIONAL,
ENVIRONMENT, SAFETY AND HEALTH (OSH)
RESPONSE OF MICRO, SMALL AND MEDIUM SCALE
ENTERPRISES (MSMEs) AND BASIC SCHOOLS IN
THE PREVENTION OF THE SPREAD OF COVID-19 IN
OBUASI (WEST) MUNICIPAL, GHANA**

*AUTHORS: JANIX KWABENA ASARE,
DATE: DECEMBER, 2020*

Abstract:

COVID-19 surge has caused deaths and had impacts on the productivity and growth of MSMEs and the education sector. How well do workers and employers of MSMEs who form 82% of the working population in Ghana who are exposed to people from different locations identify hazards related to COVID-19 and mitigate them? How well do MSMEs and basic schools comply with the OSH laws of the Labour Act 651 of Ghana, Regulations 2003 in preventing the spread of COVID-19 in Obuasi Municipal, a community with increasing COVID-19 cases?

In order to assess the safety climate of twenty (20) MSME's and five (5) basic school's response to COVID-19 in the Obuasi Municipal in Ghana, this study used interview questionnaires, open-ended discussions and observations to identify common hazards related to working conditions; working activities; employers and employee's safety behaviour and other OSH response towards the prevention of spread of COVID-19 and beyond. OSH education was then provided for employers and employees in order for them to identify hazards of COVID-19 and mitigate them.

This study discovered that lack of OSH policy, poor procedures, poor communication, poor commitment and leadership from management, poor supervision, inadequate sanitation resources and training, secondary workload and tasks and poor working environment led to poor safety climate of MSMEs and basic schools in the Obuasi

Municipal to identify and mitigate hazards in order in response to the COVID-19 surge.

This study recommends implementation of the OSH laws of Labour Act 651 of Ghana for regular OSH workplace inspections for risk assessment, passing a new integrated national OSH Law that ensures are institutions implement OSH policy including an insurance and welfare scheme as solutions to ensure that workers are healthy, safe and insured. This study also recommends safety and health training and provision of PPE to all schools and MSMEs.

Introduction

An effective Health and Safety Management System is priceless because it saves lives and more. Report by (Hämäläinen , Takala , & Kiat, 2017) revealed that in total, it is estimated that more than 7,500 people die every day; 1,000 from occupational accidents and 6,500 from work-related diseases. COVID-19, a biohazard and a pandemic is threatening lives, businesses and development since it affects the growth of MSMEs and the education sector. The Labour Act 651, Regulations 2003 of Ghana (Section 118-120) enforces that employers ensure that workers work under satisfactory, safe and healthy conditions. Research by Amoah and Amoah (2018) discovered that the MSMEs in Ghana employed about 82% of the working population in the Ghana.

Various studies done globally indicate that Micro and Small and Medium Enterprises MSMEs face different difficulties when it comes to occupational health and safety (Gardner et al., 1999; Jørgensen et al., 2010; Lamm, 1997; Micheli and Cagno, 2010; Stevens, 1999; Tait and Walker, 2000). Different studies have considered physical and chemical hazards in large companies with few on biological hazards. There should be concern for Basic Schools because they are environments with diverse group of people-children as students and adults as workers. As at Wednesday, 20th May, the Obuasi Municipal had 381 COVID-19 cases representing the highest and 43.1% of the entire

885 cases in the Ashanti Region of Ghana according to the Ashanti Regional Health Directorate.

However, in Ghana, most studies in OSH have focused on the OSH guidelines, institutional environment and regulations without focusing on biohazards like COVID-19 and hazard identification in order to assess the risk at workplace in order to draw the attention of authorities to the severity of the problems of OSH in organizations and the need to implement a new national OSH policy in Ghana.

Some studies also report that OSH difficulties in MSMEs stem from poor management of risk and inadequate resources to match the extent of the hazards present (Micheli and Cagno, 2010; Walters, 2004). Furthermore, other researchers (Brown and Trevino, 2012; Clarke, 1999) recommend that perceptions of senior managers "attitudes and behaviours is associated with OSH, well-being of workforce cements the foundation for the safety behaviour of employees and employers" preparedness to identify and mitigate hazards.

For COVID-19, the (ILO, 2020) suggest Risk Assessment, Management and Communication after considering Policy, Planning and organization. This involves assessing the risk of potential for interaction with workers, contractors, customers and visitors at the workplace and contamination of work environment, and implement measures. How well do schools know the key messages and actions for COVID-19 prevention and control in schools developed by the WHO, UNICEF and IFRC in March, 2020?

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study was to assess the current safety climate of MSMEs and basic schools in the Obuasi Municipal in Ghana and their compliance with Labour Act 651 of Ghana and to draw the attention to the severity of the problems of OSH in organizations and the need for risk assessment to mitigate hazards related to the spread of COVID-19.

The specific objectives were: (a) to identify and assess the common occupational hazards

related to working conditions and working activities associated with the spread of COVID-19 in MSMEs and basic schools in Obuasi, Ghana; (b) to investigate employers and employees behaviour towards OHS; (c) to determine how MSMEs and basic schools address OHS issues, and; (d) to provide education for employers, employees and students in order to equip them to identify hazards and mitigate them.

Significance of the Study

Less information is available on hazard identification and risk assessment in the workplaces and schools in Ghana. This study will make available knowledge of physical inspection to identify hazards and assess risk of COVID-19 and biohazards spread at workplaces of MSMEs and basic schools in Ghana and Africa in general adding to other research works which focused on the OSH guidelines, institutional environment, OHS legislation, regulation setting, International Labour Organization (ILO) Conventions.

Background

The studies were conducted during May and July, 2020 and the data collected from twenty (20) random chosen MSMEs consisting of 126 workers located at business centres away from the main town and five basic schools.

The number of MSMEs interviewed constituted the seven MSMEs sectors: Security and Doors (2); Fashion (Salon, Barbering Shop, Clothing) (4); Electronics, Computers, Accessories & Repairs (3); Phones, Accessories and Mobile Money (4); Printing Press and Photo Studio (3); Fuel Stations with Washing Bays (2); Mart and Retail Shop (2); (see Table 1).

All the five basic schools assessed were Pre-School to Junior High (Middle) School level. However, only the final year teachers and students of the Junior High (Middle) School level were allowed by order of the President of the Country to prepare and sit for the final basic school examinations.

Methods

The study implemented a diverse approach method. According to Creswell (2003), mixed methods are especially advantageous when studying OHS because they cover quantitative data (example, number of PPEs, sanitation resources provided and illness rates) in combination with qualitative concepts (awareness, attitudes and behaviour etc.).

Observations were done, respondents either MSME or school Owners, Managers and or Workers (with permission from Superior) were interviewed. Questionnaires and open-ended discussions were used to obtain information on the workplace characteristics, working conditions, workers, safety behaviours and job or working activities. 50% of people who represented their MSMEs in the study and Education were workers, 10% were managers and 40% of them were owners. All the head teachers of these basic schools were interviewed. Students were asked questions on sanitation practices to prevent the spread of the disease.

As advised by ILO, 2020 as the first step to fighting COVID-19, a sample OSH Policy document drafted using the WHO Workplace guidelines for COVID-19 were then presented to MSMEs. MSMEs were then educated on the need for risk assessment and an OSH management System referring to the provided

policy document. Schools heads and representative teachers were presented COVID-19 OSH Policy softcopy document drafted using the WHO, UNICEF and IFRC key messages and actions for COVID-19 prevention and control in schools developed in March, 2020. During the interview and open-ended discussion we educated the heads and representative teachers on how to control hazards not taken care of using the Policy document provided. In the future there will be monitoring and evaluation of the implementation of the Policy provided to MSMEs and schools.

All MSMEs studied were representative of MSMEs as defined by the Ghana Statistical Service (GSS) based on the number of employees an enterprise has employed at any point in time to categorize enterprises to be micro, small and medium enterprises. According to GSS, an MSME is defined as any enterprise or business entity that has between 1 to 5 workers as micro, an enterprise that has between 6 to 30 workers as small, an enterprise that has between 31-100 workers as medium and an enterprise that has more than 100 workers as large enterprise. Majority 15 (75%) of the enterprises we studied were located away from the central business area with the remaining 5 (25%) located close to the main business areas.

Results of the Study
Results for MSME's Assessed in May, 2020

Table 1.1: OSH findings of 126 workers of MSMEs

DESCRIPTION	YES/ REGULARLY	MAYBE/ SOMETIME S	NO/ NEVER	COMMENT S
Percentage of workers with medical conditions	0%	0%	100.0%	Okay
Percentage of workers 60 years and older	4.0%	0%	96.00%	Okay
Percentage of workers who have travelled since COVID-19 surge	9.50%	0%	90.50%	Issue
Percentage of workers who had nose mask on	18.25%	0%	81.75%	Issue
Percentage of workers who had hand sanitizers	43.65%	0%	56.35%	Issue
Percentage of workers known to have pets or rear animals	15.07%	0%	84.93%	Issue
Percentage of workers registered under an insurance scheme	52.38%	0%	47.62%	Issue

Table 1.2: OSH findings of 20 MSMEs

DESCRIPTION	YES/ REGULARLY	MAYBE/ SOMETIME S	NO/ NEVER	COMMENT S
MSMEs who had knowledge of the Labour Act	5%	20%	75%	Issue
MSMEs with welfare, compensation or sick pay scheme	35%	15%	50%	Issue
MSMEs who practiced Social Distancing	45%	50%	5%	Issue
MSMEs who promoted regular hand washing	60%	0%	40%	Issue
MSMEs who provided running water dispensers and soap	55%	0%	45%	Issue
MSMEs who disinfected surfaces and objects regularly	50%	0%	50%	Issue
MSMEs who had posters promoting sanitation	5%	0%	95%	Issue
MSMEs who provided workers substitute nose mask	85%	0%	15%	Okay
MSMEs who provided tissue paper for workers & customers	55%	10%	35%	Issue
MSMEs who provided closed bins at workplace	70%	20%	10%	Okay
MSMEs who have asked employees to stay home	10%	0%	90%	Okay
MSMEs who had employees who buy food or drink outside	90%	0%	10%	Issue
MSMEs who had employees who have supported persons suspected or infected with COVID-19	5%	0%	95%	Okay
MSMEs who measured employers, customers & contractors' temperature	5%	0%	95%	Issue
MSMEs who had an isolation room or area	10%	25%	65%	Issue

Table 1.3: Other OSH findings of 20 MSMEs

DESCRIPTION	OPTION 1	OPTION 2	OPTION 3
Waste Disposal methods of MSMEs	Refuse Damp	Refuse Damp & Burning	Burning Only
	80%	5%	15%
Breakdown of the role of people who represented MSMEs in study & education	Staff Only	Managers	Owners or employers
	50%	10%	40%
Workers Statistics	Highest Number of. Workers	Average	Lowest
	37	6.3	2
Percentage of Highest Educational Qualification of Workers or employees in MSMEs	Tertiary	SHS/ Professional Certificate	JHS/ Primary
	45%	45%	10%
Tasks expected for work at a time	Only Primary	Secondary Task	N/A
	30%	70%	
Highest working experience of Workers in MSMEs	> 2 years	1-2 years	<1 year
	70%	15%	15%
Business activities (Physical Interaction, Services; Receiving physical cash or cheque; Receiving mobile money/online payments)	All activities	Excluding mobile/online payments	N/A
	90%	10%	

Results for the basic schools assessed in June, 2020

Table 2.1 Background of the schools

QUESTION	OPTIONS	RESPONSE	COMMENTS
Type of School	Pre-school to Junior High(Middle) School	All 5 schools	Okay
Do you monitor attendance of students	Yes	All 5 schools	Okay
Learning continuity plan have you adopted	No plan	3 schools	Issue
	Social Media (WhatsApp)	2 schools	
Staff Population	a. Population of JHS Staff allowed at all five schools	29	Okay
	b. Staff population Average at all five schools	5.8	Okay
	c. Staff population Range at all five schools	5-7	Okay
Student Population	a. Population of JHS students allowed at all five schools	61	Okay
	b. Student population Average at all five schools	12.2	Okay
	c. Student population Range at all five schools	5-19	Okay
Total number of vulnerable people (staff 60 years & >, students/staff with medical conditions such as diabetes, heart and lung disease)		1 staff over 60 years	Okay
Educational qualifications of staff	i. Primary	1 School	Okay
	ii. Senior High School to Tertiary	All 5 schools	
Working Experience of staff	2 years or less	All 5 schools	Okay

Table 2.2 Knowledge of Covid-19 Control and Prevention

QUESTION	OPTIONS	RESPONSE	COMMENTS
Which COVID-19 institutional guidelines are Head Teachers aware of?	a. Ghana Education Service (GES) COVID-19 guidelines.	4/5	Okay
	b. Guidelines from the Ghana's Labour Act, World Health Organization (WHO), Ghana Health Service (GHS), UNICEF or UNESCO.	None	Issue
Which of the following groups has the school provided education on coronavirus?	Staff	All 5 schools	Okay
	Students	All 5 schools	Okay
	Guardians	2 schools	Issue
How do you address the Mental Health/Psychosocial support needs of students/staff	Staff discussion	All 5 schools	Okay
	Peer support	No school	Issue
	External agency	No school	Issue
Which of the following helplines are you aware of	Not aware of any helpline	All 5 schools	Issue

Table 2.3 Safety Behaviours

QUESTION	OPTIONS	RESPONSE	COMMENTS
Tasks expected of a worker at a time	Only Primary Task	All 5 schools	Okay
How often do you promote and demonstrate regular hand washing and positive hygiene behaviors and monitor their uptake	Entry	All 5 schools	Okay
Staff and students with Nose Mask on at time of interview	Yes	95%	Issue
Is social distancing (1m) being practiced?	Yes	1 school	Issue
	Somehow	4 schools	
Have you advised anyone with even a mild cough or low-grade fever (37.3 C or >) to stay home and take medication or have parents reported such and allow child to stay home?	Yes	1 school	Okay
How often is building Disinfection is done?	Once by AngloGold Ashanti Malaria Control Group or Zoomlion	All 5 schools	Okay
How often are objects and surfaces cleaned?	Break /closing time(s)	1 school	Issue
	Mornings	3 schools	
	None	1 school	
How often do you measure the temperature before they enter your facility?	Always	4 schools	Okay
	Never	1 school	Issue
Have you supported persons who may be at risk, and support them, without inviting stigma?	Never	All schools	Okay
How do you ensure trash, waste tissue, mask & water is disposed of safely dispose collected?	Refuse Dump	All 5 schools	Okay
	Burning in Open	2 schools	Issue
Is there an increase air flow and ventilation where climate allows	Windows opened	All 5 schools	Okay

Table 2.4 Sanitation Facilities

QUESTION	OPTIONS	RESPONSE	COMMENTS
Hand rubs placed in classrooms & exits.	Yes	All 5 schools	Okay
Dispensers/ soap, tissue paper and running water are placed in prominent places around the workplace?	Purchased by school	1 school	Okay
	Provided by GES with 4 gallons of soap for each school	4 schools	
How many schools had displayed posters promoting safety	Yes	No school	Issue
Are there closed bins available for hygienically disposing tissues/face mask?	Yes	3 schools	Issue
	No	2 schools	
Where do students and staff get their drink or food from?	Home	All schools	Issue
	Outside school sponsored by GES	All schools	Issue
Do you have thermometer gun?	Yes	4 schools	Okay
	No	1 school	Issue
Have you identified a room/area for isolation and transfer suspected persons	Yes	All 5 schools	Okay

Table 2.5 Other Safety and Health Concerns

QUESTION	OPTIONS	RESPONSE	COMMENTS
Encouraged Staff and students to register under an unexpired insurance scheme (SSNIT, NHIS)?	Yes	All 5 schools	Okay
Is there a compensation, welfare or sick-pay scheme for COVID-19 infection or death?	No response	2 schools	Issue
	No scheme	3 schools	Issue
Other Health and Safety needs of Interest	Training	3 Schools	Issue
	Other PPE	2 schools	Issue
	Fire Extinguishers	3 schools	Issue
	First Aid Box	1 school	Okay

© GSJ

Discussion of Results for MSMEs

Educational Qualification of Staff in relation to OSH management

Although 90% of all MSMEs had Owners, Managers and Workers with Tertiary and Senior High School (SHS) qualifications, only 5% of all MSMEs had knowledge of the existence of the Labour Act 651 of Ghana but no knowledge of the OSH Laws of the Labour Act, while only one MSME Owner had knowledge of safety. Only Salons and barbering shops had few workers with low education level of Junior High School (JHS). This meant enforcement of OSH measures to prevent the spread of COVID-19 was something new to most MSMEs.

Education on good OSH Safety climate such as ensuring good safety behaviours, proper working conditions and job hazard analysis was easier because the educational levels of Owners, Managers and Workers was SHS and above. The high educational qualification of respondents may help in future education, enforcements of OSH laws and management systems and build up Safety cultures of MSMEs.

Main hazards in MSME sectors and mitigation measures (See details in Table 4 below)

According to evidence by Liu J, Liao X, Qian S et al (2020) and Chan J, Yuan S, Kok Ket al. (2020), COVID-19 is transmitted through respiratory droplets and contact routes with other infected persons.

The MSMEs in the Doors and Security sector had four (4) major peculiar hazards but had three (3) mitigation measure to reduce the risk of infection and spread of the coronavirus at the workplace.

The MSMEs in the fashion sector especially Seamstress and apprentices faced five (5) main hazards but had only provided one control measure that is provision of water dispensers and running water.

The workers in the Fuel Stations with washing bays had implemented most mitigation measures as high as (6) to overcome three (3) hazards identified.

The workers in the Electronics, Computers, and Accessories & Repairs sector faced most hazards of seven (7) hazards but had only provided hand sanitizers for workers.

The workers in the Phones and Accessories, Mobile Money; as well as the Printing Press and Photo Studio sector both had six (6) hazards but only the latter enforced social distancing therefore were at high risk of exposure and spread of COVID-19.

MSMEs workers in the retail and mart sector faced four (4) major hazards but only provided water dispensers, soap and tissue for regular hand washing.

Number of Workers exposed to COVID-19

The average number of workers per all twenty (20) MSMEs was 6.3 workers and MSME with the highest number of 37 workers was a filling station with a washing bay. The highest numbers of workers were in the in sectors such as Fuel Stations with Washing Bays (42); Fashion (34); and Security and Doors (23). Therefore, a shift system was recommended for MSMEs with large number of workers.

Working Activities, workload or task that exposed workers to COVID-19

While only 10% of all MSMEs did not accept mobile or online payments, the business activities of the remaining 90% MSMEs involved risky tasks such as physical interactions, provision of services and goods and acceptance of physical cash, mobile/online and cheque payment.

It was observed that Salon workers and barbers had no gloves on although their job required physical contact. However, salon workers were safer than barbers because of regular hand-washing as required by their job.

70% of all workers had more than two-years working experience in their role. 70% of all MSMEs allowed their workers to perform both primary and secondary tasks at a time therefore workers may not focus on one task as well as monitor customers, contractors and other workers to comply to safety regulations. For instance, it was observed in a Mart that while a shop attendant was attending to one customer, another customer entered and touched items in the mart which the shop attendant did not identify without the customer washing his hand with soap and running water before entry into the mart. However, MSMEs in the sectors like the Fuel stations with washing bays had large number of workers (42) workers who performed only one primary task.

Safety Behaviours and supervision

According to evidence by Liu J, Liao X, Qian S et al (2020) and Chan J, Yuan S, Kok Ket al. (2020), COVID-19 mostly transmitted through respiratory droplets and contact routes. EU-OSHA recommends that, often, basic personal hygiene measures and wearing personal protective equipment (PPE) provides adequate protection against biological agents such as COVID-19.

Although 85% of MSMEs regularly provided workers with nose mask, only 18.25% of all 126 workers had nose mask on during our observations even though some workers were interacting with customers, co-workers and managers.

Only 45% of all MSMEs actively practiced social distancing while 50% practiced social distancing in their own way and the remaining 5% did not practice social distancing at all. 50%, half of all MSMEs disinfected surfaces and objects regularly. MSMEs with large number of employees like the Security and Doors; and Fuel Stations with washing bays strictly practiced social distancing because they were aware of their numbers.

However, it was observed that it was difficult to practice social distancing among Seamstress since apprentices had to get closer to observe and practice what was being taught. It was observed that some of the MSMEs shared items for use with closer MSMEs such as cooking pots and others.

Because of the safety climate built in response to COVID-19. MSMEs who were not supervised did not obey safety regulations. It was observed and confessed by workers at the filling stations with washing bays that they only obeyed safety regulations when the owners and managers were around to enforce them.

Working Conditions and Sanitation Resources

55% of all MSMEs had provided water dispensers and soap at their workplace however, 55% of MSMEs provided tissue papers and 60% of MSMEs promoted regular handwashing of employees, customers and contractors. A Regression output of 0.4922 calculated indicates that only 49.22% of the variation of regular handwashing is explained by provision of water dispensers and soap (significant F value was less than 0.005).

43.65% of all workers were provided alcohol-based hand sanitizers for regular sanitizing of hands, after receiving physical cash or mistakenly touching others, objects or surfaces.

90% of all workers frequently bought food or drink from outside their workplace during break time when only 55% of the MSMEs had provided water dispensers, soap and tissue for regular hand washing and drying before re-entry into their workplaces. Most workers complained that the running water dispensers were expensive due to inflated prices. Research online and in markets revealed that these water dispensers cost as high as GH¢250 about \$US 44.60. However, most MSMEs were willing to provide their water containers for tap pipes (spigots) to be installed in them. One manager of three MSMEs complained that he had loans to pay so cannot afford the Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) and water dispensers for all his business.

Waste Management

Majority 70% of all MSMEs provided closed bins at their workplace however 80% of all MSMEs dumped their waste at refuse dump collection points, 5% of the MSMEs burned or dumped their waste while only 15% of all MSMEs burned their waste from their workplace. Two managers of MSMEs reported that they do not close their waste bins because people may use paper tissue to infect the lid of the waste bins. Two Printing Press burned their waste instead of taking the waste to the refuse dump because they reported that most of their waste were only papers.

Welfare Conditions of workers:

In case of emergencies, 65% of all MSMEs had not identified an isolation room or area in case someone is suspected of COVID-19 although 10% of all MSMEs have asked 2-3 of their workers to stay home, monitor symptoms of

COVID-19 and do laboratory test due to suspected symptoms or travel although 9.50% of all workers have travelled to other towns since COVID-19 surge.

While 52.38% of all workers were registered under an insurance scheme, 35% of all MSMEs had implemented a solid welfare, compensation or sick pay scheme at their workplace to motivate their workers to stay home, monitor symptoms of COVID-19 and do laboratory test. Two workers showed interest in registering for the Social Security National Insurance Trust Fund (SSNIT) scheme for pension benefits.

Tools to monitor and control hazards related to COVID-19

5% of all MSMEs had posters promoting sanitation practices. Also, 5% of all MSMEs had temperature instruments to monitor the temperature of employers, customers & contractors. However, the manager of one of the Fuel Stations with washing bays reported that they were expecting temperature guns from their mother fuel supplying company. Some owners were interested in buying temperature guns but the cost was very high for them. The cost was highly inflated as ₵GH1,500 about US\$267 while prices online was as low as ₵GH 200 about US\$35.7 200. One manager of a barbering store who had only Junior High School education yet seemed learned had discussed with the owners of other MSMEs to contribute so that they purchase temperature guns to monitor the temperatures of employers, customers & contractors of business center.

Other findings related to COVID-19

Only 15.07% of workers interviewed were known to have pets or reared animals. One MSME reared 15 animals at the workplace. Only few of the workers said they had locked

pets in cages while the others prevented their pets from moving outdoors. Most MSME owners, managers and workers were not aware of the COVID-19 Emergency Helplines and hotspots in the Obuasi Municipal (View map below). One manager of three MSMEs reported in order to avoid overcrowding; he held meetings with only departmental heads.

Discussion of results for basic schools

Background of the schools

All the five schools were basic schools from Pre-school to Junior High (Middle) School levels. However, only the final year Junior high school students and their school staff were allowed by the government to go to school to prepare for their final Basic Education Certificate Examinations (B.E.C.E) organized by the West African Examinations Council (WAEC). Therefore, only 61 students representing 3.1% of the entire student population of all the five schools of 1970 students were allowed. 29 staff representing 31.18% of the entire staff population of all the five schools of 93 staff was allowed.

It was of no doubt that it was easier for all these five schools to monitor the student attendance since few students were allowed to attend school. Safety and health measures must be well ensured at all these five schools should the government authorize the commencement of full operation for these five schools due to the high population range of 300-500 students for these five schools. It was also observed that these schools had confined and limited school space not more than an acre which could cause crowding due to poor supervision.

Knowledge of COVID-19 Control and Prevention

4 out the 5 Head Teachers of these schools were aware of the COVID-19 school guidelines provided by the Ghana Education Service (GES).

The one remaining school was not aware of the GES guidelines due to problems of poor communication between the GES, the school management and the school staff.

However, none of them was aware of the safety guidelines from the Ghana's Labour Act, World Health Organization (WHO), Ghana Health Service (GHS), UNICEF or UNESCO. Therefore we presented the heads and representative teachers with softcopy of COVID-19 OSH Policy document drafted using the WHO, UNICEF and IFRC key messages and actions for COVID-19 prevention and control in schools they developed in March, 2020. During the interview and open-ended discussion we educated the heads and representative teachers on how to control hazards not taken care of using the Policy document provided.

Although all schools had organized a meeting or education for COVID-19 awareness and control for their staff and students, two (2) schools had involved the parents and the guardians of the students as to how to practice good hygiene at home. No school had taken steps to address the Mental Health/Psychosocial support needs of students/staff through Peer support or asked help from an External agency. Also, no school was aware of the helplines of the Ambulance Service and Ghana Health Service so it was provided to them. Students from all five schools answered correctly most of the sanitation practices they had been taught at school and through mass media.

Safety Behaviours

All five (5) schools allowed their staff to perform only their primary task at a time. Their staff promoted and demonstrated regular hand washing and positive hygiene behaviors; and monitored their uptake when entering the school building. It was identified that 5% of Staff and students did not have nose mask on during the interview. This was because they complained about difficulty breathing due to the nose mask.

It was observed that social distancing (1 metre) was strictly enforced by only one school. The rest of the schools practiced social distancing in their own way. Only one school had advised one of their students with mild cough or low-grade fever to stay home and take medication or have parents reported such and allow child to stay home. This was the one and same school that had not received sanitation resources from the GES due poor communication.

All five schools had their school building disinfected once by AngloGold Ashanti Malaria Control Group or Zoomlion before the commencement of school. However, four schools often disinfected objects and surfaces before school, during break and closing times but one school did not regularly disinfect objects and surfaces.

Only the one school that had problem with communication to access sanitation resources from the GES reported that they did not measure the temperature of before anyone entered their school because they had no temperature gun. It was the same school that had asked an ill student to stay home. However, no case of COVID-19 was reported at that school. All schools had their students and staff bringing in drink or food from home and from outside to the school and food sponsored by the GES.

All five schools ensure trash, waste tissue, mask & water collected were disposed off safely at the Refuse Dump but two of the schools also practiced burning in open air instead of taking the solid waste to Refuse Damp. Also, all liquid waste was channeled into drainage systems. To increase air flow and ventilation when climate allowed, all five schools had opened their windows.

Sanitation Facilities

All five schools had hand rubs placed in classrooms and exits. However, only four

schools had received 14-20 bottles of 200mL hand rubs from the Ghana Education Service. 70% of the students also had their personal hand rubs.

Apart from one school that purchased its Dispensers / soap, tissue paper and placed running water in prominent places. The remaining four schools had these items provided by the GES. These four schools were provided with four gallons of soap each. Three (3) out of the five (5) schools had closed bins available for hygienically disposing tissues/face mask.

None of these schools had displayed posters promoting safety. Four of these schools had temperature guns which were provided by the GES. All schools had identified a room/area for isolation and transfer suspected persons because they had enough unused classroom and outside space.

Other Safety and Health Concerns

All school head reported that they encouraged all students and teachers to register and renew the National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS) to absorb the cost of some illness in case of emergency at school. Schools did not show photocopies or records of the NHIS of the teachers and students. Since it was demanded by the laws of the country for all staff, all the schools reported that they had their staff registered under the Social Security National Insurance Trust (SSNIT). None of the five schools reported compensation, welfare or sick-pay scheme for COVID-19 infection, death, other diseases or accidents.

Three school heads showed interest in Safety and Health training. Two schools showed interest in other Personal Protective Equipment (PPE); three schools requested for fire extinguishers and one school needed First Aid Box.

Appendix

Figure 1.1: Map of Cases of COVID-19 in blue dots at Obuasi (West) Municipal.

Table 1.4: Analysis of hazards and mitigation measures by sectors of MSMEs

Type of sector	Number of MSMEs	Peculiar Main Hazards Identified that should be mitigated	Number of workers at Risk	Mitigation measures in place
Security and Doors	2	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Travel during COVID-19 surge 2. No welfare, compensation or sick pay scheme 3. Had employees 60 and above 4. High number of employees 	23	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Majority of workers had nose mask on 2. Social distancing properly enforced 3. MSMEs had water dispensers, soap and tissue so practice regular had washing
Fashion (Salon, Barbering Shop, Clothing)	4	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Most workers performed secondary task 2. Poor enforcement of social distancing 3. Workers had pets 4. High number of employees 5. Majority of workers were not wearing nose mask 	34	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. MSMEs had water dispensers, soap and tissue so practice regular had washing
Electronics, Computers, Accessories & Repairs	3	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Workers were not wearing nose mask 2. Two of the MSMEs had no welfare, compensation or sick pay scheme 3. Two of the MSMEs don't regularly disinfect objects and surfaces 4. Two of the MSMEs had no water dispensers, soap and tissue so did not practice regular hand washing 5. Two of the MSMEs workers had pets 6. No welfare, compensation or sick pay scheme 7. Social distancing properly enforced 	6	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Majority of workers had hand sanitizers
Phones and Accessories, Mobile Money	4	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. All workers performed secondary task 2. Workers were not wearing nose mask 3. No clear isolation area or room identified 4. Three of the MSMEs don't regularly disinfect 	6	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Low number of employees

		<p>objects and surfaces</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Three of the MSMEs had no water dispensers, soap and tissue so did not practice regular hand washing Three MSMEs had not provided closed bins 		
Printing Press and Photo Studio	3	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> All workers performed secondary task Workers were not wearing nose mask Two of the MSMEs don't regularly disinfect objects and surfaces Two of the MSMEs had no water dispensers, soap and tissue so did not practice regular hand washing No isolation areas or rooms identified Two of the MSMEs burned their waste 	7	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Low number of employees Social distancing properly enforced
Fuel Stations with Washing bays	2	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Large number of employees Workers were not wearing nose mask No isolation areas or rooms identified 	42	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> All workers performed only one primary task Existence of welfare, compensation or sick pay scheme Social Distancing is enforced Regularly disinfected objects and surfaces MSMEs had water dispensers, soap and tissue so practiced regular hand washing MSMEs had provided closed bins
Mart and Retail Shop	2	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> All workers performed secondary task Workers were not wearing nose mask No welfare, compensation or sick pay scheme Social distancing not clearly enforced 	8	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Low number of employees MSMEs had water dispensers, soap and tissue so practiced regular hand washing

Figure 1.2: A graph of OSH Risk Assessment of 126 workers of MSMEs in Obuasi municipal

Figure 1.3: A graph of OSH Risk Assessment of 20 MSMEs in the Obuasi municipal

References

- Chan J, Yuan S, Kok Ket al. A familial cluster of pneumonia associated with the 2019 novel coronavirus indicating person-to-person transmission: a study of a family cluster. *Lancet* 2020. doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(20)30154-9
- Creswell, J.W., 2003. *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Method Approaches*, second ed. Sage, London
- EU-OSHA. (n.d.). *Risk assessment for biological agents*. Retrieved from European Agency for Safety and Health at Work: <http://osha.europa.eu/en/topics/riskassessment>
- Gardner, D., Carlopio, J., Fonteyn, P.N., Cross, J.A., 1999. Mechanical equipment injuries in small manufacturing businesses. Knowledge, behavioural, and management issues. *Int. J. Occup. Saf. Ergon.* 5 (1), 59–71.
- GSS, *Integrated Business Establishment Survey, Regional Spatial Business Report*, Ghana Statistical Service, Accra, Ghana, 2016.
- Hämäläinen , P., Takala , J., & Kiat, T. B. (2017). *Global Estimates of Occupational Accidents and Work-related Illnesses*. 1500 Bendemeer Road: Workplace Safety and Health Institute.
- Harms-Ringdahl, L., 2001. *Safety Analysis: Principles and Practice in Occupational*
- ILO. (2020, 9, 4). *Prevention and Mitigation of COVID-19 at Work, Action Checklist*. International Labour Organization.
- Jørgensen, K., Duijm, N.J., Troen, H., 2010. Accident prevention in SME using ORM. *Saf. Sci.* 48 (2010), 1036–1043.
- Lamm, F., 1997. Small businesses and OH&S advisors. *Saf. Sci.* 25, 153–161. Metrology Act, 2004. RT I, 31.12.2010, 26. <<https://www.riigiteataja.ee/akt/131122010026>> (12.04.13).
- Liu J, Liao X, Qian S et al. Community transmission of severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2, Shenzhen, China, 2020. *Emerg Infect Dis* 2020. doi.org/10.3201/eid2606.200239
- Micheli, G.J.L., Cagno, E., 2010. Dealing with SMEs as a whole in OHS issues: warning from empirical evidence. *Saf. Sci.* 48 (2010), 729–733.
- Seth Kwaku Amoah, Alfred Kwabena Amoah. The Role of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) to Employment in Ghana. *International Journal of Business and Economics Research*. Vol. 7, No. 5, 2018, pp. 151-157. doi: 10.11648/j.ijber.20180705.14. Received: August 10, 2018; Accepted: September 7, 2018; Published: October 11, 2018
- Stevens, G., 1999. Features – workplaces injuries in small and large manufacturing workplaces – an analysis of the risks of fatal and non-fatal injuries, including figures for 1994/5–1995/6. *Labour Market Trends* 107, 19–26.
- Tait, R., Walker, D., 2000. Marketing health and safety management expertise to small enterprises. *Saf. Sci.* 36, 95–110.